

A CASE STUDY ABOUT THE COMPARISON BETWEEN THE CHENNAI PORT AND THE JAWAHARLAL NEHRU PORT

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Abstract:

India has a coastline spanning 7516.6 kilometers, forming one of the biggest peninsulas in the world. According to the Ministry of Shipping, around 95 per cent of India's trading by volume and 70 per cent by value is done through maritime transport. It is serviced by 13 major ports, 200 notified minor and intermediate ports. The total 200 non-major ports are in the following States:- Maharashtra, Gujarat, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala, Andhra Pradesh, Odisha, Goa, West Bengal, Daman and Diu, Lakshadweep, Pondicherry, and Andaman & Nicobar. Since the subject chosen for the case study is on Chennai port trust and Jawaharlal Nehru trust, it may not be possible to present the complete import & export statistics of the port trust. The main objective is to compare the infrastructure & technology of Chennai port trust & Jawaharlal Nehru trust port.

Introduction and Design of the Study:

Government of India plans to model these ports and has approved a project called sagarmala. The ports and shipping industry in India plays a vital role in sustaining growth in the country's trade and commerce. The Indian Government has allowed Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) of up to 100 per cent under the automatic route for port and Harbor construction and maintenance projects. The government has also initiated National Maritime Development Programme (NMDP), an initiative to develop the maritime sector with a planned outlay of US\$ 11.8 billion.

Indian Ports Association:

Indian Ports Association (IPA) was constituted in 1966 under Societies Registration Act, primarily with the idea of fostering growth and development of all Major Ports which are under the supervisory control of Ministry of Shipping. Over the years, IPA has consolidated its activities and grown strength by strength and considered to be a think tank for the Major Ports with the ultimate goal of integrating the maritime sector.

Shipping:

Major ports handled over 74% of all cargo traffic in 2007. All major ports, except one Ennore Port are government administered, but private sector participation in ports has increased. There are also 7 shipyards under the control of the central government of India, 2 shipyards controlled by state governments, and 19 privately owned shipyards. As of 2000, there were 102 shipping companies operating in India, of which five were privately owned and based in India and one was owned by Shipping Corporation of India. There were 639 government-owned ships, including 91 oil tankers, 79 dry cargo bulk carriers, and 10 cellular container vessels. Indian-flagged vessels carried about 15 percent of overseas cargo at Indian ports for financial year 2003.

Future of Indian Ports:

Will Indian port sector really see the emergence of private sector as a major player in the port sector in the future? Will major ports be fully corporative, and bring about greater rationalization and transparency in functioning? Are minor ports in India poised to take a lead over performance of major ports? Is there enough room for new green field port projects in Indian port sector? Several of these questions loom large, as the Indian port sector is increasingly coming under the impact of wide ranging port reforms and private sector investments, in line with larger transformations underway in many global ports. The development of the port sector is important to development of maritime trade is an axiom that no nation can afford to ignore in today's globalised world. This was equally true in the distant past, when maritime nations undertook extensive overseas maritime explorations and trade to set their mark on global economic history. Needless to say, some of the world's most developed nations have also been among the most important maritime nations of the world, actively involved in global maritime trade. India's shipping and port sector saw dramatic growth in the first four decades of post independence, under the initiative of planned development and active government support. More than two-thirds of the port cargo handling capacity and more than half of India's national shipping tonnage were established in

the first four decades of independence. However, with a basically inward looking economic policy perspective that emphasized more on self-reliance and import-substituting development strategies, the overall trade and technology-driven growth of the economy remained constricted. However, with the paradigm shift in economic policy since early nineties, the government has sought to liberalize the port sector by opening it to private sector investments. As a result, ports have now begun to assume a more proactive role as facilitators of trade with a range of value-added service offerings in terms of cargo handling efficiency and actively seeking to improve their performance with international ports.

Importance of Ports in Economic Development:

Infrastructure is understood as an important input for industrial and overall economic development. While this is certainly true, there is no clear definition of infrastructure according to the current usage of the term in India. As per the Economic Survey, the following sectors constitute infrastructure

- ✓ Power: Electricity generation
- ✓ Coal production
- ✓ Petroleum production: crude oil and refinery throughput
- ✓ Cement production
- ✓ Railways: Revenue-earning goods traffic and passenger kilometers
- ✓ Ports: Cargo handled at major ports
- ✓ Civil Aviation: Cargo and passengers handled at Airports Authority
- ✓ Roads: Length of roads and length of National Highways; and India (AAI) airports;
- ✓ Telecommunications: New telephone connections approved

Objective of the Study:

- ✓ To know about the geographic factors of Indian ports.
- ✓ To compare the infrastructure & technology of Chennai port trust & Jawaharlal Nehru trust port.
- ✓ To identify the lagging indicators of Chennai Port trust.
- ✓ To suggest measures for the improvement of the Chennai port trust in par with Jawaharlal Nehru port trust.

Statement of the Problem:

- ✓ Since the subject chosen for the case study is on Chennai port trust and Jawaharlal Nehru trust, it may not be possible to present the complete import & export statistics of the port trust.
- ✓ There is no proper analysis the time period is very shortly the data sources are secondary data analyses.

Research Design:

The current study is based on Case study method a very popular form of qualitative analysis involves a careful and complete observation of a social unit, be that unit a person, a family, an institution, a cultural group or even the entire community. It is a method of study in depth rather than breadth. The case study places more emphasis on the full analysis of a limited number of events or conditions and their interrelations. The case study deals with the processes that take place and their interrelationship. Thus, case study is essentially an intensive investigation of the particular unit under consideration. The object of the case study method is to locate the factors that account for the Behavior-patterns of the given unit as an integrated totality. The current study is conducted with a case example of Chennai port trust and the Jawaharlal Nehru port trust.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Jawaharlal Nehru Port Import & Import in Statistics Report:

Commodity	2014-15	2015-16	% Variation Over Previous Year
Liquid Bulk	6,189,644	6,504,656	5.09
Cement & Other Dry Bulk Cargo	652,584	674,064	3.29
Break Bulk	25,709	58,109	126.03
Total Bulk	6,867,937	7,236,829	5.37

Vessels Handled:

Types of Vessel *	In Nos	
	2014-15	2015-16
CONTAINER: JNPCT	663	678
: NSICT	593	555
: APMT	672	616
: NSIGT	--	86
DRY BULK	40	39
BREAK BULK	148	241
LIQUID – At berth	526	562
– At JNP Anchorage		3
TOTAL	2,642	2,780

Chennai Port Import & Export Statistics Report:

Commodity	2013 – 2014	2014-2015	2015 - 2016	2016-2017 (UptoJan17)
Liquid Bulk	15084	14050	13519	15027
Dry Bulk	8322	8778	7759	7041
Break Bulk	3090	3054	2998	2853
Containers	31804	29040	28861	33046
Overall	15001	15444	15756	15896

Vessels Handling:

Commodity	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017 (UptoJan2017)
Liquid Bulk	429	427	445	334
Dry Bulk	165	175	151	151
Break Bulk	429	426	382	267
Containers	780	762	755	596
Total	1804	1790	1733	1348

Export Data of India, India Customs Data and Trade Statistics:

Import Data of India, India Customs Data and Trade Statistics:-

Findings:

- ✓ The Jawaharlal Nehru port was the fourth terminal to develop with a budget of 7915 crores, whereas the Chennai port trust is only developing as the second terminal.
- ✓ The Jawaharlal Nehru port trust websites have container tracking technology, whereas Chennai port trust does not have container tracking technology.
- ✓ The Jawaharlal Nehru port trust has a total area 3000+hectares while the Chennai port trust has only 587 hectares.

- ✓ Jawaharlal Nehru port trust have the 12 berths only, but the Chennai port trust has 24 berths and draft ranging from 12 to 16.5m.
- ✓ The Jawaharlal Nehru port trust has adopted the technology like the Fixed Fire Fighting System Mobile Fire Fighting System and such technology is not available in Chennai port trust.
- ✓ The Chennai port trust website has more information than Jawaharlal Nehru port trust.

Suggestion:

- ✓ The Chennai port trust is now developing as a second terminal. With more new cargo handling equipment, it can have a third terminal.
- ✓ The Chennai port trust develop website page similar to the Jawaharlal Nehru port trust that has information like SEZ, documentation, container tracking technology etc.,
- ✓ The Chennai port trust have the 587 hectares only but the Jawaharlal Nehru port trust has the 3000+ hectares for the warehouse, storage container etc., With further expansion, the above facilities can also be included in the Chennai Port Trust.
- ✓ The Jawaharlal Nehru port trust has utilised the berths because of the very high container turn over. The Chennai port trust has 24 berths which can be better utilized.
- ✓ The Chennai port trust has to develop service in the marine service, shipping service, society responsibility and fire safety.

Conclusion:

According to the analysis of comparison statement and its interpretation is the need of the hour for all the ports across the India. True is the case in the Chennai port trust & the Jawaharlal Nehru port trust also. In order to compete with global economic scenario and to sustain its place, port need to monitor its technology continually and improve infrastructure at all the times. This in turn, requires a sound appraisal of management with critical evaluation as technology, infrastructure and programmes. The port should follow the cluster model, to reap the economics of large scale import & export

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